

Supplemental material for
**Global vs Local Optimization of Precast Concrete Fabrication and Erection using
Digital Twin Construction**

Jiyuan Li, Timson Yeung, Sivan Grodsky, Davide Schaumann, Ph.D., and Rafael Sacks,
Ph.D., M.ASCE

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Figs. S1–S7 and Tables S1–S10, along with detailed descriptions of the integrated production–transportation optimization model, genetic algorithm implementation, and validation procedures, are available online at Zenodo:

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The supplementary materials include:

- Mathematical formulations for wall and slab production–transportation models
- Model integration for local and global optimization scenarios
- Genetic algorithm (GA) design, encoding, and operators
- Feasibility adjustment and repair mechanisms
- Validation experiments and system parameter settings

A time-lapse video of the physical simulation experiment is available at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MdFbxwOuOiE>

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Precast Construction Workflow Optimization Framework

This section presents the integrated optimization framework developed to model and improve the full precast construction workflow, from factory production, through transportation, to on-site erection. The framework is designed to support both local and global optimization strategies under DTC-based planning environments. It incorporates real-world constraints, component dependencies, and phase-specific priorities, enabling systematic evaluation of different coordination and control approaches. The structure of the framework reflects the complexity of multi-phase decision-making in precast projects, while maintaining flexibility for scenario testing and performance comparison.

Overview of the Two-Step Optimization Strategy

Scheduling problems in precast construction are NP-hard, especially when production, transportation, and on-site erection are interdependent. Prior studies have shown that both production scheduling and erection sequencing require significant computational effort, with heuristic methods such as GAs often employed to obtain near-optimal solutions within practical timeframes (Wang et al. 2023).

A fully integrated optimization of all stages would cause exponential growth in the solution space, making exact heuristic approaches computationally prohibitive. Conversely, decomposing the stages and optimizing them hierarchically risks suboptimal system-wide performance due to local optima.

To balance computational feasibility with global coordination, this research adopted a two-step global optimization framework:

1. **Erection Sequence Enumeration:** A heuristic enumeration procedure generates a set of constructible erection sequences using a mixed-heuristic strategy combining wall continuity, block-by-block, floor-by-floor, and zone-by-zone principles. Each enumerated sequence explicitly encodes spatial constraints to ensure constructability.
2. **Optimization of Production and Transportation:** For each enumerated erection sequence, an optimization model is formulated to determine production and transportation plans that minimize total project cost. The mathematical formulation of this model is presented in Section 6.2, while the GA implementation used to solve it is detailed separately in Chapter 7.

Mathematical Model for Integrated Production–Transportation Optimization

The optimization model integrates the planning of wall and slab elements within a unified framework. Each component type is produced in a dedicated factory with distinct operational rules, walls on casting tables and slabs on long-line hollow-core beds, but both are interdependent through the erection sequence at the construction site. The model is formulated as an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) problem that minimizes setup, inventory, transportation, and delay costs.

Both the local and global scenarios operate at the piece level; however, their treatment of delay differs. The local scenario assumes static, factory-site independence, where delays are computed individually for each piece without cross-factory coordination. The global scenario introduces interaction among factories and the site through apartment-level sequencing, where delays are aggregated based on spatial and temporal dependencies among components.

Note that because the wall and slab factories follow distinct operational constraints, their mathematical formulations are presented separately in the following sections.

Assumptions

To ensure realistic representation of precast workflows, several shared assumptions and operational rules are applied:

- Setup dependence: Setup time and cost depend solely on dimensional differences between consecutive components. Changes in rebar layout do not affect setup cost.
- Discrete setup function: The additional mold-change time between two consecutive walls is approximated as a discrete step function of their dimensional difference. Small changes (0–1 differing dimensions) are absorbed within normal operations and incur no extra setup time. Larger changes (2–3 differing dimensions) require a dedicated mold reset and incur one full workday of setup.
- Non-interrupted production: Once a precast element begins production, it proceeds without interruption until completion.
- Curing delay: Each produced element requires a full curing cycle before being eligible for delivery.
- Unlimited transportation capacity: The number of available trucks is not a limiting factor in scheduling.
- Sequential dispatch: Deliveries are dispatched at the start of each workday, prior to on-site erection (practically equivalent to overnight delivery).

Wall Model

The notation system for the wall model is summarized in **Table S1** to Table S4.

Table S1 defines the sets and indices used to represent wall components, production tables, and time dimensions.

Table S2 lists the parameters and constants governing production, setup, transportation, inventory, and delay costs.

Table S3 presents the decision variables that describe assignment, sequencing, and timing decisions for each wall component.

Table S4 introduces the derived variables representing factory and site inventory levels over time.

The objective function, expressed in **(1)**, minimizes the total cost of wall production, transportation, and on-site handling, including setup, inventory, and delay penalties. Cost components are formulated in **(2)–(9)**, while **(10)–(15)** establish the operational constraints:

(10) ensures that each wall component is assigned to exactly one production table; (11)–(12) define sequencing and time-continuity relationships between walls produced on the same table, preventing overlapping operations; (13) enforces that delivery occurs only after production and curing are completed; and (14)–(15) impose upper limits on factory and site inventory capacities, maintaining feasible storage levels.

Together, these formulations constitute the complete ILP model for integrated wall production–transportation optimization.

Table S1: Sets and indices used in the wall model.

Sets and indices	Definitions
W	Set of wall components, indexed by i and j
M_w	Set of wall production tables, indexed by m
i, j	Indices for wall components
m	Index for wall production table
d	Index for day

Table S2: Parameters and constant used in the wall model.

Parameters	Definitions
t_{wall}^{prod}	Production duration of wall components
$DimDiffWall(w_i, w_j)$	Number of differing dimensions (0–3) between consecutive walls w_i and w_j
$t_{setup,unit}^{wall}$	Unit time for wall mold dimension change is
t_{curing}^{wall}	Curing time of wall components
$t_{delivery}$	Transportation duration from factory to site
e_i	Erection time of wall i
C_{setup}^{wall}	Wall set up cost
$C_{inv}^{factory,wall}$	Wall factory inventory cost
C_{tran}^{wall}	Wall transportation cost
$C_{inv}^{site,wall}$	Wall site inventory cost
$C_{delay}^{piece,wall}$	Wall piece delivery delay penalty
$C_{setup,unit}^{wall}$	Unit cost of wall set up
$C_{inv,unit}^{factory,wall}$	Unit cost of wall set up

Parameters	Definitions
$c_{tran,unit}^{wall}$	Unit cost of wall transportation
$c_{inv,unit}^{site,wall}$	Unit cost of wall site inventory
$c_{delay,unit}^{piece,wall}$	Unit cost of wall piece delivery delay
N_d^{wall}	Number of wall pieces assigned to be delivered at day d
$Q_{vehicle}^{wall}$	Maximum number of wall pieces can be loaded onto one truck
M	A sufficiently large constant used for linearization
$MaxL_{fac,wall}$	Maximum allowed factory inventory level for wall pieces
$MaxL_{site,wall}$	Maximum allowed on-site inventory level for wall pieces

Table S3: Decision variables defined in the wall model.

Decision variable	Definitions
$z_{i,m} \in \{0, 1\}$	1 if wall i is assigned to production table m , 0 otherwise
$y_{i,j,m} \in \{0, 1\}$	1 if wall i produced before wall j on production table m , 0 otherwise
$p_i^{start} \in Z$	Production start time of wall i
$d_i^{start} \in Z$	Delivery start time of wall i

Table S4: Derived variables calculated in the wall model.

Derived variable	Definitions
$WallFacInv(d)$	Number of wall components stored in the factory at day d ; increases when a wall finishes curing and decreases when it is dispatched for delivery.
$WallSiteInv(d)$	Number of wall components stored in the on-site inventory at day d ; increases upon delivery arrival and decreases when the corresponding wall is erected.
$t_{i,j}^{setup}$	Setup time between consecutive wall i and j

The objective function minimizes the total cost associated with wall production, transportation, and on-site handling. The total cost Z^{wall} comprises setup, factory inventory, transportation, site inventory, and delay penalties, as expressed in (1)

$$\min Z^{wall} = C_s^{wall} + C_{inv}^{factory,wall} + C_t^{wall} + C_{inv}^{site,wall} + C_d^{piece,wall} \quad (1)$$

Each cost component and derived variable is defined in Equations

(a) Setup Cost and Time

setup costs occur when consecutive production tasks on the same table require mold changeover. A setup time is incurred only when wall i is immediately followed by wall j on the same production table.

The setup time between walls i and j is defined as:

$$t_{i,j}^{setup} = \begin{cases} 0, & DimDiffWall(w_i, w_j) \leq 1 \\ 1, & DimDiffWall(w_i, w_j) \geq 2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The total setup cost over all production tables is:

$$C_{setup}^{wall} = c_{setup,unit}^{wall} \sum_{m \in M_w} \sum_{i \in W} \sum_{j \in W} DimDiffWall(w_i, w_j) \cdot y_{i,j,m} \quad (3)$$

(b) Factory Inventory Cost

A wall enters factory inventory after curing and remains there until delivery starts. The factory inventory level at day d is:

$$WallFacInv(d) = \sum_{i \in W} I(P_i^{start} + t_{wall}^{prod} + t_{curing}^{wall} \leq t \leq d_i^{start}) \quad (4)$$

Where $I(\cdot)$ denotes the indicator function, equal to 1 if the condition holds and 0 otherwise. The total factory inventory cost is:

$$C_{inv}^{factory,wall} = \sum_d c_{inv,unit}^{factory,wall} \cdot WallFacInv(d) \quad (5)$$

(c) Transportation Cost

Transportation cost is proportional to the number of required truck loads per day:

$$C_{tran}^{wall} = c_{tran,unit}^{wall} \sum_d \left(\left\lceil \frac{N_d}{Q_{vehicle}} \right\rceil * Q_{vehicle} - N_d^{wall} \right) \quad (6)$$

(d) Onsite Inventory Cost

Walls delivered to the site before erection contribute to on-site inventory. The inventory level and cost are:

$$WallSiteInv(t) = \sum_{i \in W} I(d_i^{start} + t_{delivery} \leq t \leq e_i) \quad (7)$$

$$C_{inv}^{site,wall} = \sum_d C_{inv,unit}^{site,wall} \cdot WallSiteInv(d) \quad (8)$$

(e) Late delivery penalty cost

Delivery delays are penalized based on the difference between actual erection and delivery times:

$$C_d^{piece,wall} = c_{d,unit}^{piece,wall} \sum_{i \in W} \max(0, e_i - d_i^{start} - t_{delivery}) \quad (9)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{m \in M_w} z_{w_i,m} = 1, \forall i \in W \quad (10)$$

$$p_{w_j}^{start} \geq p_{w_i}^{start} + t_{w_i} + t_{i,j}^{setup} - M(1 - y_{i,j,m}), \forall i, j, m \quad (11)$$

$$p_{w_i}^{start} \geq p_{w_j}^{start} + t_{w_j} + t_{j,i}^{setup} - M(1 - y_{j,i,m}), \forall i, j, m \quad (12)$$

$$d_{w_i}^{start} \geq p_i^{start} + t_{wall}^{prod} + t_{curing}^{wall}, \forall i \in W \quad (13)$$

$$WallFacInv(d) \leq MaxL_{fac,wall}, \forall t \quad (14)$$

$$WallSiteInventory(d) \leq MaxL_{site,wall}, \forall t \quad (15)$$

Slab model

The notation system for the slab model is summarized in **Table S5 – Table S8**.

Table S5 defines the sets and indices used to represent slab components, production lines, batches, and time dimensions.

Table S6 lists the parameters and constants governing production, setup, batching, transportation, inventory, and delay costs.

Table S7 presents the decision variables that describe assignment, batch scheduling, and delivery timing for each slab component.

Table S8 introduces the derived variables that represent batch composition, factory and site inventory levels, and the batch-to-slab mapping logic.

The objective function, expressed in (25), minimizes the total cost associated with slab production, transportation, and on-site handling, including setup, inventory, and delay penalties.

Cost components are detailed in (17) – (23), while (25) – (33) establish the operational constraints ensuring the feasibility of production sequencing, batching, and delivery logistics.

Specifically, (25) assigns each slab to exactly one batch on one production line; (26) enforces batch cross-section uniformity; (27) constrains total slab length within the mold capacity; and (28) ensures the within-batch length differences satisfy the tension requirement. (29) links each slab’s production start time to its corresponding batch; (30) maintains production time continuity between consecutive batches; and (31) guarantees that delivery begins only after curing is completed. Finally, (32) – (33) impose capacity limits on factory and site inventories, ensuring realistic stacking and handling conditions.

Together, these formulations constitute the complete ILP model for integrated slab production–transportation optimization under the DTC framework.

Table S5: Sets and indices used in the slab model.

Sets and indices	Definitions
S	Set of slab components, indexed by p and q
N_s	Set of slab production lines, indexed by n
B_n	Batch indices on line n , indexed by b (no empty “gaps”)
b	Index for batch of each production line
p, q	Indices for slab components
n	Indices for slab components
d	Index for day

Table S6: Parameters and constant used in the slab model.

Parameters	Definitions
t_{slab}^{prod}	Production duration of wall components
$t_{b,b+1,n}^{setup}$	Slab mold changing time from batch b to slab $b + 1$ on production line n
$DimDiffSlab(b, b + 1)$	Number of differing dimensions (0–2) between slabs batch b and $b + 1$
σ_p	Cross-section of slab p
L_p	Length of slab p
L^{max}	Length of slab production line

Parameters	Definitions
ΔL	Minimal length difference allowed in production batch regarding strength requirement
$t_{setup,unit}^{slab}$	Unit time for wall mold dimension change
t_{curing}^{slab}	Curing time of wall components
$t_{delivery}$	Transportation duration from factory to site
e_p	Erection time of slab p
C_{setup}^{slab}	Slab set up cost
$C_{inv}^{factory,slab}$	Slab factory inventory cost
C_{tran}^{slab}	Slab transportation cost
$C_{inv}^{site,slab}$	Slab site inventory cost
$C_{delay}^{piece,slab}$	Slab piece delivery delay penalty
$C_{setup,unit}^{slab}$	Unit cost of slab set up
$C_{inv,unit}^{factory,slab}$	Unit cost of slab set up
$C_{tran,unit}^{slab}$	Unit cost of slab transportation
$C_{inv,unit}^{site,slab}$	Unit cost of slab site inventory
$C_{delay,unit}^{piece,slab}$	Unit cost of slab piece delivery delay
N_d^{slab}	Number of slab pieces assigned to be delivered at day d
$Q_{vehicle}^{slab}$	Maximum number of slab pieces can be loaded onto one truck
$MaxL_{fac,slab}$	Maximum allowed factory inventory level for slab pieces
$MaxL_{site,slab}$	Maximum allowed on-site inventory level for slab pieces
M	A sufficiently large constant used for linearization

Table S7: Decision variables defined in the slab model.

Decision variable	Definitions
$x_{p,b,n} \in \{0, 1\}$	1 if slab p assign to batch b on production line n , 0 otherwise
$p_{b,n}^{start} \in \mathbf{Z}$	Production start time of batch b on production line n

Decision variable	Definitions
$d_p^{start} \in Z$	Delivery start time of slab p

Table S8: Derived variables calculated in the slab model.

Derived variable	Definitions
$WallFacInv(d)$	Number of wall components stored in the factory at day d ; increases when a wall finishes curing and decreases when it is dispatched for delivery
$WallSiteInv(d)$	Number of wall components stored in the on-site inventory at day d ; increases upon delivery arrival and decreases when the corresponding wall is erected
S_b	Batch composition set contains slabs in batch b
p_p^{start}	Production start time of slab p , consistent with the batch assigned

Objective function for slab production and transportation model

The objective function minimizes the total cost associated with wall production, transportation, and on-site handling. The total cost Z^{slab} comprises setup, factory inventory, transportation, site inventory, and delay penalties, as expressed in

$$\min Z^{slab} = C_{setup}^{slab} + C_{inv}^{factory,slab} + C_{tran}^{slab} + C_{inv}^{site,slab} + C_{delay}^{piece,slab} \quad (16)$$

Each cost component is defined in Equations

(a) Setup Cost

For two consecutive slab batches S_{b-1} and S_b assigned to the same production line n , the difference is based on width and height:

$$t_{b,b+1,n}^{setup} = DimDiffSlab(b, b+1) \cdot t_{setup,unit}^{slab}, \forall n, b = 1, \dots, (B_n - 1) \quad (17)$$

$$C_{inv}^{factory,slab} = \sum_n \sum_{b=1} t_{b,b+1,n}^{setup} \cdot C_{setup,unit}^{slab} \quad (18)$$

(b) Factory Inventory Cost

$$SlabFacInv(d) = \sum_{p \in S} I(p_p^{start} + t_{slab}^{prod} + t_{curing}^{slab} \leq t \leq d_p^{start}) \quad (19)$$

$$C_{inv}^{factory,slab} = \sum_d C_{inv,unit}^{factory,slab} \cdot SlabFacInv(d) \quad (20)$$

(c) Transportation Cost

$$C_{tran}^{slab} = C_{tran,unit}^{slab} \sum_d \left(\left\lceil \frac{N_d^{slab}}{Q_{vehicle}^{slab}} \right\rceil \cdot Q_{vehicle}^{slab} - N_d^{slab} \right) \quad (21)$$

(d) Onsite Inventory Cost

The stack number $SlabSiteInv(d)$ will be incremented when the precast piece is delivered to the site and will be decremented when the erection time is reached.

$$SlabSiteInv(d) = \sum_{p \in S} I(d_p^{start} + t_{delivery} \leq t \leq e_p) \quad (22)$$

$$C_{inv}^{site,slab} = \sum_d C_{inv,unit}^{site,slab} \cdot SlabSiteInv(d) \quad (23)$$

(e) Late delivery penalty cost

$$C_{delay}^{piece,slab} = C_{delay,unit}^{piece,slab} \cdot \sum_p Max[0, e_p - d_p^{start} - t_{delivery}] \quad (24)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{n \in N_s} x_{p,b,n} = 1, \forall p \in S \quad (25)$$

$$x_{p,b,n} + x_{q,b,n} \leq 1, \forall p \neq q \text{ with } \sigma_p \neq \sigma_q \quad (26)$$

$$\sum_{p \in S} L_p * x_{p,b,n} \leq L_n^{max}, \forall n, \forall b \quad (27)$$

$$|L_{S_p} - L_{S_q}| - \Delta L \leq M(2 - x_{p,b,n} - x_{q,b,n}), \forall n, b, \forall p \neq q \quad (28)$$

$$p_p^{start} = \sum_n \sum_b p_{b,n}^{start} x_{p,b,n}, \forall p \in S \quad (29)$$

$$P_{b+1,n}^{start} \geq P_{b,n}^{start} + t_{slab}^{prod} + t_{b,b+1,n}^{setup}, \forall n, b = 1, \dots, B_n - 1 \quad (30)$$

$$d_p^{start} \geq P_{b,n}^{start} + t_{slab}^{prod} + t_{b,b+1,n}^{setup} \quad (31)$$

$$SlabFacInv(d) \leq MaxL_{fac,slab}, \forall d \quad (32)$$

$$SlabSiteInventory(d) \leq MaxL_{site,slab}, \forall d \quad (33)$$

Model Integration for Applying Global and Local Optimization

In 0 and 0 the wall and slab models were specified independently, representing the local optimization perspective. Under this mode, each factory minimizes its own piece-level costs without inter-factory or site coordination. Consequently, site inventory levels are computed relative only to each component's planned erection time, neglecting cross-component prerequisites between walls and slabs.

In contrast, the global optimization scenario introduces full coordination among factories and the construction site. Walls and slabs are optimized jointly, and a component can be erected only when all prerequisite components in its dependency set have been completed.

To capture this interdependency, the site inventory formulation is extended to reflect logical readiness rather than simple physical availability:

$$IntegratedSiteInv(d) = \sum_{p \in S} I(d_p^{start} + t_{delivery} \leq t \leq ReadyToErect(p, t))$$

where:

- S is the set of all the precast pieces in the project
- $ReadyToErect(p, t)$ is a Boolean function that returns true if all prerequisite components for slab p have been erected by time t

Accordingly, this study introduces the Apartment Delivery Delay Cost as a key component of the global optimization objective function. This cost is calculated based on the cumulative deviation from planned apartment completion targets at predefined checkpoints. This approach emphasizes flow reliability and continuity over total project duration.

Then, the cumulative apartment delivery delay cost is:

$$C_d = \sum_k \max(T_{planned}(a_k) - T_{actual}(a_k), 0) \cdot C_{delay,apartment}^{unit}$$

Where:

- A be the set of all apartments,

- $T_{\text{planned}}(a_k)$ be the planned cumulative number of apartments to be completed by checkpoint k ,
- $T_{\text{actual}}(a_k)$ be the actual cumulative number of apartments completed by checkpoint k ,
- $C_{\text{delay,apartment}}^{\text{unit}}$ be the unit cost of delay per apartment per checkpoint.

This formulation penalizes uneven delivery flow, even if the final project duration is acceptable. It reflects real-world consequences such as idle finishing crews, delayed inspections, and missed handover deadlines, issues that arise when apartment completions fall behind cumulative targets.

GA Implementation

Figure S1: GA flow chart.

This chapter presents the design and implementation of the GA developed for local and global optimization of integrated wall and slab production-delivery scheduling in a precast construction environment. The algorithm serves as the computational core of the proposed DTC optimization framework, designed to evaluate, adapt, and improve scheduling decisions under complex interdependencies among factory production, logistics, and on-site erection.

Two GA variants were developed within a shared algorithmic GA framework to support different levels of integration: a local optimization GA, which treats the wall and slab factories as independent decision-making entities, and a global optimization GA, which evaluates system-wide performance under a unified objective. Both variants share the same chromosome representation, genetic operator set, and feasibility-preserving design; the difference lies in the scope of information available during fitness evaluation and the inclusion of an integrated feasibility adaptation step in the global model.

The GA flow chart as illustrated in Figure S1. The algorithm begins with encoding and initial population generation, followed by iterative cycles of genetic operator application, feasibility adaptation, and integrated schedule repair (for the global case) until the stopping criterion is satisfied, producing either locally optimized (independent) or globally coordinated (integrated) precast schedules. The following sections elaborate on the detailed structure of the GA implementation, including the solution

encoding, genetic operator design, constraint-handling mechanisms, and fitness evaluation procedures applied in both the local and global optimization modes.

Solution Encoding

The GA employs a structured hierarchical encoding scheme to represent the integrated wall and slab production–delivery scheduling problem in a form consistent with real precast workflows. Each candidate solution in the population is encoded as a nested dictionary structure that captures both resource assignments and timing information for wall and slab elements. This encoding flexibly models multiple production resources and their time-dependent activities, enabling simultaneous optimization of sequencing and scheduling decisions across factories while maintaining their distinct operational characteristics.

The hierarchical structure is illustrated in Figure S2, showing the Python-style dictionary format that defines production, delivery, and arrival times for each element in the wall and slab subsystems. The encoding comprises three key components: (1) the assignment component, defining the allocation of elements to production resources and their processing sequence; (2) the temporal component, recording start and finish times for production and delivery activities to support cost evaluation; and (3) the integrated structure, representing walls and slabs independently while coordinating them under shared delivery and on-site erection constraints. This encoding provides a direct mapping between the digital chromosome and real construction processes, ensuring that the optimization model remains interpretable and traceable within the DTC environment. Because it already reflects the actual scheduling state of all elements, no separate decoding step is required and fitness evaluation is performed directly from the encoded structure.

```
solution = {
  "wall": {
    'table_assignments': {table_i: [wall_id_1, wall_id_2, ...]},
    'wall_production_start_times': {wall_id: start_time},
    'wall_production_finish_times': {wall_id: finish_time},
    'wall_delivery_start_times': {wall_id: delivery_start},
    'wall_delivery_arrival_times': {wall_id: arrival_time}
  },
  "slab": {
    'table_assignments': {line_i: [[batch_1_slabs], [batch_2_slabs], ...]},
    'slab_production_start_times': {slab_id: start_time},
    'slab_production_finish_times': {slab_id: finish_time},
    'slab_delivery_start_times': {slab_id: delivery_start},
    'slab_delivery_arrival_times': {slab_id: arrival_time}
  }
}
```

Figure S2: GA encoding structure.

Initial Population Strategy

The generation of the initial population defines the starting point of the evolutionary search and has a decisive influence on the convergence behavior of the GA. Instead of relying on purely random initialization, this study adopts a problem-aware heuristic strategy that integrates domain knowledge from precast production and erection workflows. The same initialization procedure is used for both the Local GA and Global GA. The initialization aims to achieve a balance between diversity and feasibility, ensuring that the GA begins its evolution from a realistic and varied set of production–delivery plans. Two complementary heuristics were designed to reflect competing operational goals in precast scheduling:

- **Erection-focused initialization**, which prioritizes on-time delivery by grouping wall and slab elements according to their erection deadlines. For elements with closely aligned deadlines, dimension similarity is also considered to enhance production continuity before assigning them sequentially to production resources.
- **Dimension-focused initialization**, which emphasizes production efficiency by grouping elements with similar dimensions to reduce mold setup time. Within each dimension group, elements are then prioritized according to their erection deadlines.

After the table assignments are determined, production and delivery times are generated according to predefined operational rules: (1) random start times are assigned to the first element on each table to enhance population diversity, (2) setup times are estimated based on geometric differences between consecutive elements, and (3) an adaptive Just-In-Time (JIT) delivery mechanism is applied to minimize either onsite inventory or late delivery penalties, depending on production timing. Specifically, in the Global GA, the initialized solutions are further processed through an integrated schedule feasibility adjustment procedure, which enforces installation sequencing, daily capacity limits, and apartment-level delay calculations, resulting in a fully feasible and coordinated starting population. This initialization strategy significantly enhances the GA's performance compared to random initialization by generating starting solutions that are both realistic and diverse. The use of mixed heuristics further strengthens the global search capability, helping the algorithm avoid local convergence and enabling more effective exploration of trade-offs between factory site priorities.

Integrated Schedule Feasibility Adjustment

While both local and global optimization scenarios share the same algorithmic structure, their treatment of interdependencies among elements differs fundamentally. In the local scenario, each factory operates independently, optimizing its own production and delivery schedule based on piece-level objectives. In contrast, the global scenario introduces cross-factory coordination and apartment-level dependency constraints, requiring an additional post-processing mechanism to ensure schedule feasibility before fitness evaluation. This mechanism, termed the *integrated schedule feasibility adjustment*, aligns factory-level outputs with project-level installation logic. The adjustment procedure verifies and corrects the temporal and

spatial feasibility of the combined wall and slab schedules by referencing a predefined dependency topology, which encodes the hierarchical and spatial relationships among all precast elements through zone-floor groupings and constraint rules. This relational map defines installation precedence. For example, vertical wall elements must be erected before their dependent horizontal slabs, and lower floors must be completed before upper floors can begin. Using this relational map, the algorithm enforces sequencing rules such as floor-by-floor progression, vertical-before-horizontal (V-before-H) logic, and daily erection capacity limits to ensure that all installations follow realistic construction order. Figure S3 describes an example of the vertical–horizontal dependency adjustment. The wall element (V1001) serves as a prerequisite for all dependent slab elements (H1009–H1014). If V1001 is delayed until day T , the erection of all associated slabs must also be postponed to no earlier than day T to maintain installation feasibility.

Figure S3: An example of integrated schedule feasibility adjustment.

Genetic Operators and Individual Feasibility Repair

The genetic operators form the core of the evolutionary search process, driving diversification and gradual improvement of scheduling solutions. In this study, operators are designed according to two complementary scheduling philosophies, Push and Pull, which reflect the fundamental tradeoff between tardiness reduction and inventory minimization in production–delivery systems.

Push-type Operators

Push-type operators advance production or delivery activities to earlier points in time. Their primary goal is to reduce tardiness penalties by ensuring elements are produced and delivered before their erection deadlines. However, these early shifts often lead to increased inventory holding costs, as components may remain idle in the factory or onsite storage. Typical push-type operations include:

- Advancing production start times (e.g., shifting walls or slabs to begin earlier within feasible bounds)

- Eliminating idle gaps between consecutive production tasks to improve casting table utilization.
- Accelerating deliveries to secure early availability of elements at the construction site.

These operators are especially effective in deadline-driven environments, where the project's overall objective prioritizes on-time completion over temporary increases in inventory.

Pull-type Operators

Pull-type operators delay production or delivery activities toward their latest feasible times, following JIT principles. Their goal is to minimize inventory accumulation both in factories and onsite, while still maintaining overall schedule feasibility. By postponing operations closer to their consumption points, pull-type strategies align production flow with erection progress. Typical pull-type operations include:

- Delaying production to reduce factory inventory without causing late deliveries
- Deferring deliveries to synchronize arrivals with erection sequences
- Applying batch-level JIT adjustments, where entire production lines are shifted later to align with the latest erection requirements.

These operators embody a lean manufacturing perspective, emphasizing waste reduction and synchronized flow between upstream and downstream processes.

Interaction with Feasibility Repair

Both operator categories promote diverse scheduling behavior, yet their aggressive temporal adjustments may violate production, curing, or delivery constraints. To address this, the algorithm employs a hierarchical feasibility repair mechanism that automatically restores consistency after each mutation. Adjustments at higher workflow levels cascade through dependent stages – shifts in production sequences propagate to start and finish times, recalibrating delivery schedules accordingly. If a delayed production task invalidates a delivery, the mechanism assigns the earliest feasible alternative satisfying curing and erection requirements. Unlike conventional GA repairs that discard infeasible offspring, this mechanism embeds domain knowledge into the repair logic, ensuring robustness and enabling broader exploration without sacrificing feasibility. Thus, all retained individuals remain constructible and comparable in cost evaluation. As illustrated in the Figure S4, a swap mutation moves element V1009 from casting table 2 to casting table 1, creating infeasibility due to a missing setup step between different dimension types. The feasibility check detects and flags this issue, after which the hierarchical repair mechanism inserts the required setup and shifts subsequent tasks to restore constructability. The final repaired solution satisfies all production and curing constraints, demonstrating how customized mutation combined with hierarchical repair supports diverse search while maintaining operational validity.

Figure S4: An example of individual solution feasibility repair mechanism.

Fitness Evaluation

Each solution is evaluated through a cost function defined over the simulated project timeline. For local optimization scenarios, the function is expressed as:

$$Total\ Waste_{local} = C_s + C_{inv}^{factory} + C_t + C_{inv}^{site} + C_d^{piece}$$

For global optimization scenarios, where penalties are aggregated at the project level, the function is expressed as:

$$Total\ Waste_{global} = C_s + C_{inv}^{factory} + C_t + C_{inv}^{site} + C_d^{project}$$

This formulation captures the major trade-offs in precast planning, including setup effort, factory and onsite inventory holding costs, transportation costs, and penalties for late delivery.

GA Validation

To validate the proposed GA, a series of six controlled test cases were designed. Each test controls one or multiple cost items to observe whether the algorithm responds with logically expected behaviors. The observation focused on pieces' actual production and delivery start dates combining factory inventory level and onsite inventory levels over time, as this information helps to observe the flow of pieces through the system.

Table S10 summarizes the scenarios, including the dominant cost component(s), parameter adjustments, and the expected behavior based on rational planning logic. "N/A" indicates that no specific behavior is anticipated in that dimension for the given scenario. The results show that the solutions found by the algorithm successfully reflect the expected behaviors across all seven scenarios, indicating that the algorithm is reliable.

Case study background

The case study was based on a residential precast concrete building project named *Postiaukio* in Helsinki, Finland. The original structure comprised eight stories, two elevator and stairwell cores, 61 apartments, and a total of 1,300 precast pieces across a 5,000 m² gross floor area. This project was selected because it captures the complexity of precast assembly processes, including diverse element types, spatial and technical constraints, and inherent variances in work quantities between locations. The 1:25 scale laboratory model replicates this building, enabling participants to interact directly with precast elements to simulate erection activities. In the computer simulation, the same case provides a basis for modelling workflow disruptions such as quality defects and delivery delays (see Figure S5 and Figure S6).

To complement the case data, an interview was conducted with the project manager of the *Postiaukio* precast residential project to obtain realistic estimates of production, logistics, and scheduling parameters. The discussion provided insights into key operational constraints, including truck capacity, delivery frequency, and delay penalties, which were used to define the system parameters summarized in the next section. The manager reported that each truck typically transported five precast elements per trip, with transportation and handling representing a notable cost factor. The average cost of a precast wall element was estimated at approximately €200/m³, compared to €100/m³ for in-situ concrete, implying that about €100/m³ is attributed to mold setup, reinforcement assembly, and overhead. The project manager also indicated that apartment-level delay penalties were approximately €5,000 per day, which served as the baseline for defining delay-related cost components in the optimization model. These empirical inputs anchored the simulation parameters to realistic industry practices, ensuring that the modeled cost relationships reflected the economic logic of the original project.

Calibration Results from Physical Simulation

Calibration relied on empirical observations from Stage 1. Daily erection capacity was sampled from element-type-specific productivity distributions estimated from observed installation times, thereby preserving the stochastic characteristics of on-site assembly. The detailed distribution fitting results are provided in the Supplementary Material (Figure S7) to support reproducibility while maintaining the focus of the main text on the comparative analysis of optimization strategies. In addition, a time-lapse video of the physical simulation is provided at the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MdFbxwOuOiE>. The video illustrates the experimental workflow, including production, delivery, and on-site installation processes, and provides visual context for the empirical observations used in model calibration.

Figure S5: Postiaukio construction site in Helsinki, Finland.

Figure S6: BIM model of the Postiaukio residential building.

Figure S7: Distribution of installation cycle time by element type from physical simulation

System Parameters

The system parameters define the cost components and operational limits that determine the fitness of each candidate solution within the GA. These values were determined based on interviews with the project manager of the *Postiaukio* precast residential project in Helsinki, Finland. The cost parameters were normalized with respect to the setup cost (divided by 100), and the accumulated cost in each optimization run represents the relative measure of waste generated during the process, including waiting time, idle truck dispatching, and delay.

Table S9: System parameter settings

Parameter	Value	Source	Remarks
Set up cost	1.0 (normalized)	Estimated (see case study background)	Estimated from the typical cost difference between concrete material and precast product, represents mold preparation and transition overhead.
Factory inventory capacity	100 pieces	Direct observation	NA
Factory inventory cost	0.2 (normalized)	Inferred Interview	A normalized baseline cost used for relative comparison across cost components; serves as the reference for site inventory (10× higher).
Site inventory capacity	35 pieces	Direct observation	NA
Site inventory cost	2 (normalized)	Inferred	Assigned a high relative value to reflect limited site space and encourage shifting storage to the factory.
Truck capacity	5 (pieces/trip)	Interview	NA
Transportation cost	10 (normalized)	Interview	NA
Apartment delivery delay penalty	50 (normalized)	Interview (see section case study background)	NA
Piece delivery delay penalty	2.5 (normalized)	Inferred	Each apartment contains roughly 20 pieces. So, the assigned cost is equivalent to apartment delay.
Start of production with respect to the start of erection	-5	Experimental design	Set to begin five days earlier to intentionally increase coupling between production and erection, thereby amplifying the importance of system-wide coordination in the experiments.

Table S10: Validation of optimization tools.

Index	Scenario	Key Parameter Adjustment	Expected Behavior				Validation
			Production behavior	Delivery behavior	Factory Inv.	Site Inv.	
1	Factory setup dominant	High setup cost	Grouped by dimensions similarity	N/A	N/A	N/A	As expected
2	Erection date dominant	High late delivery penalty	Sorted by erection date	N/A	N/A	N/A	As expected
3	Less time in factory	High factory inventory cost	N/A	Delivery starts once ready	Low	N/A	As expected
4	Pull flow (factory-driven)	High factory inventory cost; high late delivery penalty	Sorted by erection date	Delivery starts once ready	Low	N/A	As expected
5	Pull flow (site-driven)	High site inventory cost; high late delivery penalty	Sorted by erection date	Delivery arrives just-in-time	N/A	Low	As expected
6	Pull flow (system)	High factory & site inventory cost; high late delivery penalty	Produced in the last-minute	Delivery arrives just-in-time	Low	Low	As expected